

ISic3693

I.Sicily inscription 3693

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object

altar

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Melita

Place of origin (modern)

Malta

Provenance

Rabat Mdina, found 27.11.1951 'at a little distance outside the ditch which marks walls of Roman town', in an area covered with Roman tombs

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Rabat, Domus Romana

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI329927

1. χαῖρε
2. Π (ούβλιος) Αἴλιος Ἐρμόλαος
3. Περγαμηνός κωμωδός
4. καὶ λυριστής· ἐβίωσεν
5. ἔτη □ κε' □ ὑγίαινε.
6. Θ (εοῖς) Κ (αταχθονίους) .
- 7.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

PHI 329927

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 17.0438

Coleiro, Edward 1957. A Greek inscription found in Malta. *Journal of Hellenic Studies*. 77: 312-313.

Licensed under a Creative

Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-23): ISic3693. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4388968>